

Microbial Contamination Assessment of Ready to Eat Roasted Beef (Meat) Sold In Makurdi metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria

S.T., Soom¹, J.T., Hemen² and V.K Apuu,¹

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, Benue state University, Makurdi

² Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria.

Abstract-: Beef (Meat) is a highly perishable food which provides a conducive environment for the growth of many pathogenic microorganisms that can cause diseases in humans. This study was aimed at determining the microbial contamination of ready to eat roasted beef (suya-meat), sold within Makurdi metropolis. A total number of 50 ready-to-eat roasted beef (suya-meat) samples were purchased from 50 different selling points in 5 of the major public areas within Makurdi metropolis. The samples were cultured on Xylose-Lysine Deoxycholate Agar, Mannitol Salt Agar, Potato Dextrose Agar, Nutrient Agar, Eosin Methylene Blue Agar and Peptone Water. Tenfold serial dilution techniques, spread and pour plate method of inoculation were employed to determine the bacteria and fungi loads of the samples. The colonies obtained were sub-cultured repeatedly to obtain pure isolates. The isolates were identified using Morphological and Biochemical tests. For the total viable bacteria count, Wadata was observed to have the highest (1.61×10^8 cfu/ml), with Wurukum having the least (8.2×10^7 cfu/ml). The total viable fungi count was observed to be highest at North-bank (9.4×10^7 cfu/ml), while it was least at Wurukum (5.9×10^7 cfu/ml). The study reveals the isolation of the seven bacteria species: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* spp., *Enterobacter* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* recorded the highest (23.5%) occurrence rate while *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Klebsiella* spp. had the least (3.77%) rate of occurrence. The prevalence of the bacteria isolates was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). And six Fungi species were also isolated: *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Rhizopus* spp., *Candida* spp. and *Penicillium* spp. *Aspergillus niger* had the highest (36.4%) occurrence rate while *Penicillium* spp. (10.6%) had the least occurrence. The prevalence of the fungi isolates was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). On the basis of location in respect to bacteria isolates, Wadata area (32.08%) had significantly ($P < 0.05$) highest rate of isolation while, the least (7.55%) was recorded from Modern market area. This implies that, roasted beef (*Suya meat*) sold in Makurdi metropolis may serve as a potential source of diarrheal and other foodborne diseases due to the presence of those pathogenic isolates from the meat and which may render the meat unsafe for consumption. The baseline information on occurrence of these pathogens from roasted meat may be used to educate consumers on good sanitary practices during processing and selling of the roasted meat (Suya).

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1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background information about the Study

Beef have been the major supply of meat in Nigeria as a result of extensive and semi-intensive cattle production system in Nigeria by Fulani and Hausa people of the northern Nigeria. Due to the chemical composition and characteristic, meat is a highly perishable food which provides excellent source of growth of many hazardous microorganisms that can cause

infection in human and also lead to meat spoilage and economic loss. The most important bacteria meat spoilage is caused by lactic acid bacteria which is physiologically related group of fastidious and ubiquitous gram-positive organisms, these includes many species such as *Lactobacillus*, *Leuconostoc*, *Pediococcus* and *Streptococcus*. Since meat has a high nutritive value, microorganisms could easily grow on it Amadi et al.,(2016). The possible sources of

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contamination are through slaughtering of sick animals, washing the meat with dirty water, handling by butchers, contamination by flies, processing close to sewage or refuse dumps environment, spices, transportation and use of contaminated equipment such as knife and other utensils, (Rahman *et al.*, 2023).

The slaughtering process affords extensive contamination of sterile tissue with gram-negative enteric bacteria from animal intestine including *Salmonella species* and *Escherichia coli* as well as contaminant such as gram-positive Lactic cocci associated with humans, animals and the environment. *Enterococci* and *Clostridia* have been isolated from lymph node of red meat animals (Putri, *et al.*, 2023).

Microorganisms grow on meat causing visual, textural and organoleptic changes when they release metabolite (Cao, *et al.*, 2023). The microbial load in meat and meat product increases as long as growth conditions are favorable.

The factors influencing microbial growth includes acidity pH, temperature, water activity, gaseous requirement, nutrient and competition of microbes for the nutrient. Controlling these factors implies maintaining long shelf life of meat and meat product but proper preservation of meat could be achieved by the combination of two or more preservation method which includes drying, salting and high temperature (Putri, *et al.*, 2023). Despite the economic and nutritional benefits of street foods, the consumption of these roadside foods has been suggested to potentially increase the risk of foodborne diseases as street foods are readily contaminated from different sources (Andrade, *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, this study was aimed at determining the microbial contamination of ready to eat roasted beef (suya-meat), sold within Makurdi metropolis

2.0 Material and Method

2.1 Collection and Preparation of Samples

A total number of 50 ready-to-eat roasted beef samples were purchased in replicate from 50 different selling points in 5 of the major public areas within Makurdi metropolis. These areas include; Wadata, High-level, North-bank, Wurukum and Modern market area. The samples were carefully wrapped in aluminum foil papers and processed aseptically in the laboratory for bacteriological and fungal analysis.

The samples were prepared using the serial dilution method with a Ten-fold dilution of the homogenate from 10^{-4} up to 10^{-5} dilution factor as described by Devi, (2023).

2.2 Enumeration, Isolation, and Identification of Bacteria

The pour plate method was used for enumeration. Exactly 0.1 ml of the 10^{-5} serial diluents were aseptically dispensed into petri dishes and then the already prepared molten nutrient agar was added. The petri dishes were swirled gently to ensure the media and inoculum were properly mixed. All plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours in an incubator. After the incubation period, the plates were observed, and the colonies were counted with the aid of a magnifying glass and calculations were done to obtain the total viable count (Owusu-Ansah, *et al.*, 2023).

Each of the homogenates was cultured in test tubes containing peptone water as a pre-enrichment step. The tubes were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours in an incubator. The broth cultures were then sub-cultured onto the already prepared selective media using the streak plate method to obtain pure isolates (Mahunu, *et al.*, 2022).

2.3 Biochemical Tests

2.3.1 Triple Sugar Iron Test

This test employed the Triple Sugar Iron Agar. The medium was prepared according to the manufacturer's specification, and the method used was according to the procedures described by Panwar *et al.*, (2023).

2.3.2 Citrate Utilization, Indole , Catalase , Coagulase , Urease Tests,

The Simmon's Citrate agar was used for Citrate Utilization test, Peptone water was used for Indole test and the Urea base agar was used for Urease test, All the media were prepared according to the manufacturer's specifications, and the methods used were according to the procedures described by Panwar *et al.*, (2023).

2.3.3 Indole Test

Motility Test and Gram Staining

The Motility Test and Gram Staining technique were carried out in accordance with the procedures described by Hamed *et al.*, (2024).

2.4 Identification of Fungi

Both microscopic and macroscopic techniques were employed for the identification of the mold.

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The microscopic morphology was determined using Lactophenol cotton blue stain as described by Abu-Sini *et al.*, (2003).

Table 1 shows the bacteria isolated from ready-to-eat beef within Makurdi metropolis. Seven (7) different bacterial species were observed across the locations. The highest occurring bacteria were *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, each having an occurrence of 25 and collectively representing 47.2% of the total occurrence observed. This was followed by *Salmonella* spp. with 21(19.8%). *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Klebsiella* spp. were the least occurring bacteria, each having an occurrence of 4(3.8%) respectively. A significant ($P < 0.05$) relationship was observed between the bacterial isolates and their respective occurrences.

3.0 Statistical Analysis

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 20 was used for the statistical analysis of the log transformed microbial counts. Descriptive statistics mean and standard error values were expressed. A one-way analysis of variance was carried out at $\alpha = 0.05$ and Tukey test statistics was used for mean separation.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Prevalence of Bacterial Isolates from Ready-To-Eat Beef Sold Within Makurdi Metropolis.

Table 1 Prevalence of Bacterial Isolates from Ready-To-Eat Beef Sold Within Makurdi Metropolis

Bacterial Isolate	Occurrence	% Occurrence
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	25	23.58
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	4	3.77
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	25	23.58
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	21	19.81
<i>Enterobacter</i> spp.	9	8.49
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	4	3.77
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	18	16.98
Total	106	100

$$\chi^2 = 33.248; df = 6; p = 0.000$$

Prevalence of Fungal Isolates from Ready-To-Eat Roasted Beef Sold Within Makurdi Metropolis.

Table 2 shows the fungi isolated from ready to eat beef within Makurdi metropolis. Five different fungal species were observed across the locations. The highest occurring fungus was

Aspergillus niger, having an occurrence of 24 and representing 36.4% of the total occurrence observed. The least occurring fungus was *penicillium* spp. with the occurrence of 7(10.6%). A significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed between the fungal isolates and their respective occurrences.

Table 2: Prevalence of Fungal Isolates from Ready-To-Eat Beef Sold Within Makurdi Metropolis

Fungal Isolate	Occurrence	% Occurrence
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	24	36.4
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	16	24.2
<i>Rhizopus</i> spp.	9	13.6
<i>Candida</i> spp.	10	15.2
<i>Penicillium</i> spp.	7	10.6
Total	66	100

$$\chi^2 = 20.700; df = 4; p = 0.000$$

Occurrence of Bacterial Isolates Obtained from Ready-To-Eat Beef in Relation to the Locations.

Table 3 shows the occurrence of bacterial isolates obtained from ready-to-eat beef in relation to the locations. The location with the highest occurrence was Wadata with the occurrence of 34 representing 32.08% of the total occurrence. Five out of the seven bacteria identified in this study were found in this location with *E. coli* having the highest occurrence of 10. The location with the least occurrence of bacteria was Modern market with 8(7.55%). *S.aureus* and *Enterobacter* spp.were the only isolated bacteria species in this location with an occurrence of 4 each. A significant difference (P<0.05) was found between the occurrence of bacteria in ready-to-eat beef in relation to location.

Bacterial Isolates (n=106)	Occurrence at respective locations				
	North bank	Modern market	Wadata	Wurukum	High level
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	8	4	8	5	0
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	0	0	4	0	0
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6	0	10	4	5
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	6	0	6	4	5
<i>Enterobacter</i> spp.	0	4	0	5	0
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	0	0	0	4	0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	4	0	6	2	6
Total (%)	24(22.64)	8(7.55)	34(32.08)	24(22.64)	16(15.09)

$\chi^2 = 16.376; df = 6; p = 0.003$

5.0 Occurrence of Fungi Isolates Obtained from Ready-To-Eat Beef in Relation to the Locations.

Table 4 shows the occurrence of fungal isolates obtained from ready to eat beef in relation to the locations. The location with the highest occurrence was Wadata with the occurrence of 19 representing 28.79% of the total occurrence. All of the fungi identified in this study were found in this location, with *Aspergillus niger*

having the highest occurrence of 6. The location with the least occurrence of fungi was Modern market with 10(15.15%). 3 out of the 5 fungi species identified in this study were found in this location, with *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* having the highest occurrence of 4 each. No significant difference (P>0.05) was found between the occurrence of fungi in ready-to-eat beef in relation to location

Table 4: Occurrence of Fungi Isolates Obtained from Ready-To-Eat Beef in Relation to the Locations

Bacterial Isolates (n=66)	Occurrence at respective locations				
	North bank	Modern market	Wadata	Wurukum	High level
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	5	4	6	4	5
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	4	4	4	0	4
<i>Rhizopus</i> spp.	0	0	5	4	0
<i>Candida</i> spp.	5	0	1	4	0
<i>Penicillium</i> spp.	0	2	3	0	2
Total (%)	14(21.12)	10(15.15)	19(28.79)	12(18.18)	11(16.67)

$\chi^2 = 6.000; df = 4; p = 0.199$

Total Viable Count for Bacteria.

Table 5 shows the total bacteria viable count. Wadata was observed to have the highest total viable bacteria count of 1.61×10^8 cfu/ml, followed by Modern market (1.02×10^8 cfu/ml),

with Wurukum having the least (8.2×10^7 cfu/ml). There were some significant differences between some of the values when compared (p<0.05).

Location	Total plate count	CFU count(x10 ⁵)
North bank	98.13 ±19.79	9.8×10 ⁷
Modern market	102.90 ±29.61	1.02×10 ⁸
Wadata	161.20 ± 29.68	1.61×10 ⁸
Wurukum	82.27± 35.20	8.2×10 ⁷
High level	92.10 ± 50.06	9.2×10 ⁷
FLSD (0.05)	55.330	5.5×10 ⁷

Values are mean ± standard deviation.

FLSD = Fisher’s Least Significant Difference.

Total Viable Count for Fungi.

The total viable fungi count (Table 6) was observed to be highest at North-bank (9.4×10⁷cfu/ml), while it was least at Wurukum (5.9×10⁷cfu/ml). However, there was no significant difference between them when compared (p>0.05).

Location	Total plate count	CFU count(x10 ⁵)
North bank	9.40 ±5.54	9.4×10 ⁷
Modern market	6.00 ±3.37	6.0×10 ⁷
Wadata	8.56± 3.97	8.5×10 ⁷
Wurukum	5.90± 4.28	5.9×10 ⁷
High level	6.10 ± 2.73	6.1×10 ⁷
FLSD (0.05)	NS	NS

Values are mean ± standard deviation. NS=Not Significant.

Cultural Characteristics of the Bacterial Isolates.

Table 7 shows the cultural characteristics of the bacteria isolates. The bacteria were isolated using Xylose-Lysine Deoxycholate Agar, Mannitol Salt Agar and Eosin Methylene Blue Agar.

XLDA	EMBA	MSA	Suspected Isolates
No growth	No growth	Yellow	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
No growth	No growth	Colorless	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
Yellow	Green metallic sheen	No growth	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Red	Colorless	No growth	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Mucoid, yellow	Pink, without sheen	No growth	<i>Enterobacter</i> spp.
Mucoid, yellow	Pink and mucoid	No growth	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.
Pink	Colorless	No growth	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>

Key: EMBA = Eosin methylene blue agar, MSA = Mannitol salt agar, XLDA = Xylose lysine deoxycholate agar.

Cultural Characteristics of the Fungi Isolates.

Table 8 shows the cultural characteristics of the fungi isolates on Potato Dextrose Agar.

Table 8: Cultural Characteristics of the Fungi Isolates.

Isolates	Colonial characteristics
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Black
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Yellow-green
<i>Rhizopus spp.</i>	Dense cottony-fluffy growth, color is initially white, then turns grey to yellowish-brown
<i>Candida spp.</i>	Creamy white
<i>Penicillium spp.</i>	Green with white edges

Biochemical Test Results of Bacterial Isolates

Table 9 shows the biochemical characteristics of the bacterial isolates. The bacteria were identified based on sugar fermentation, citrate

utilization, Indole production, Urease production, Coagulase production, Motility, catalase production, coagulase production and Gram stain.

Table 9: Biochemical Characterization of Bacterial Isolates

Biochemical results							Organism							
Triple Sugar Iron Agar							Cit	Ind	Urea	Cat	Coag	Mot	Gram	
Slant	Butt	Glu	Suc	Lac	H ₂ S	Ga								
A	A	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	
A	A	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	
A	A	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	
K	A	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	
A	A	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	<i>Enterobacterspp.</i>	
K	A	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	<i>Klebsiella spp.</i>	
K	K	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	

Key: Glu = Glucose, Suc = Sucrose, Lac = Lactose, H₂S = Hydrogen Sulphide, Cit = Citrate, Ind = Indole, Urea =

Urease, Cat = Catalase, Coag = Coagulase, Mot= Motility, Gram = Gram’s stain. A=Acidic, K=Alkaline.

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